

Smart Phone Buying and Usage Behavior Among College Students

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Abstract

Smart phone usage has become a necessity for various purposes such as personal, academic, social networking and making financial payments etc. Smart phone is a cellular telephone with a capability to operate advanced applications and browse the internet and it allows users to install and run applications. Phone calling & sending texts are like the very basic purposes for which phones were been purchased earlier, but now a day mobiles are been used for entertainment & communication. Now, the mobile phones are coming up with variety of features like internet access, sending e-mails, games, access to social networking sites like face-book, listening to music, reading books, dictionary and so on. The students are using mobile phones for sending messages, calling even when the class is in progress. So now a day's everyone is looking out to have a smart phone. There are 5.11 billion unique mobile users in the world today, up 100 million (2%) in the past year. There are 4.39 billion internet users in 2019, an increase of 366 million (9%) versus January 2018. Smartphone usage statistics suggest that an average person spends 2 hours and 51 minutes per day on their mobile device, 22% of us check our phones every few minutes, and 51% of users look at it a few times per hour, it shows that we are getting dangerously close to becoming addicted. Smartphone's and mobile devices dictate our lives. It is scary to think that the evolution of human beings in the last century has been mainly influenced by technology. Smartphone's with android systems are generally used by college students not only for communication but also for learning and socialization. In this article the researcher studied the Smartphone buying behavior and usage behavior of college students.

Keywords: Smart Phone, students, usage behaviour, buyer, mobile

Introduction

India's telecommunication market is the second largest in the world; the mobile phone technology has brought the world closer. It provided great convenience in communication among people by way of either calling or texting. There are 3.48 billion social media users in 2019, with the worldwide total growing by 288 million (9%) since this time last year. 3.26 billion People use social media on mobile devices in January 2019, with growth of 297 million new users representing a year-on-year increase of more than 10%. Adoption of Smartphone by students of higher learning has been a global phenomenon in recent years. Mobile phones have become an essential part of everyone's day to day life since 1990s. A variety of mobile phones available in the market and also number of users increases day to day. In the modern business world due to the development of science and technology different type of new applications have been introduced in the market every year. Improvement of technology catches number of users especially students have smart phone crazy and they use new application smart phones. The taste

and preference of consumer also will change. As smart phones have become more available, they are increasingly owned and used by college students. Today's smart phones are providing its users a one step solution to all their basic needs. Many devices such as watch, camera, GPS, calculator, diary, recorder, music player, etc. have been replaced by smart phones. Students use their smart phones mainly as a tool of entertainment, social lifeline, and much more. Smartphone is a mobile phone running a complete operating system in a manner similar to a traditional computer, which offer advanced computing abilities and connectivity options. These features enable new kinds of mobile services that in turn shape the usage habits of smart phone users. As smart phones provide more and more applications for an increasingly a wider range of usage situations, they have become an increasingly integrated part of students everyday life.

Review of Literature

James and Drennan (2005) conducted a study on Australian students and identified a higher usage rate of 1.5 hours to 5 hours a day. They also highlighted the financial costs, emotional stress, damaged relationships and falling literacy as adverse consequences of excessive usage. eCycle (2012) discussed the advantages and disadvantages as learning and teaching tools, smartphone apps allow college students to access information quickly, thus increasing their college performance. Smart phones can help students create flash cards, make presentations, instantly get answers to questions, record films, record voice, and then send them to their computer. Krithika and Vasantha (2013), in their study of the mobile phone usage among teens and young adults on impact of invading technology, found that the cell phone usage is so strongly integrated into young people's behaviour that it was showing the symptoms of behavioural addiction. A survey conducted by North et al (2014) found few signs of addiction to respondent's mobile phones. Their study explored the use and role of mobile phones among South African university students. They focused on four main categories to examine the students' mobile phone use namely reasons to use mobile phones, pattern of mobile phone use, purchasing factors and behavior related issues. Martin (2010) conducted a study to determine if cell phone usage affects the student's concentration in class and the amount of information they actually receive with the distraction of cell phones, students responded that cell phone usage in class affects their concentration and the information they receive, but they feel more comfort when they can check their cell phone in class.

Objective of the Study

1. To know the smart phone brand preference among college students
2. To know the factors considered during the purchase of Smartphone
3. To understand the smart phone usage behavior among students

Scope of the study

In this study the researcher identified how smart phones influences the students day today life and why students use smart phone, and also identified the brand which is the more popular among the students. The researcher conducted the study during August to October 2019, and the data were collected from the under graduate arts and science students from Cuddalore districts

and the number of sample limited to 100, since the sample size is small, the result of this study cannot be generalized.

Research Methodology

The survey questionnaire included thirty three questions; all the questions have been used for this study. The purpose of using Smartphone was measured with Rank scale from one to eleven and type of social media most preferred by the respondents were measured with Rank scale from one to ten.

Collection of Primary Data

For the purpose of the present study, the necessary Primary data have been collected using a survey method with the help of a structured questionnaire administered in person from the respondents regarding their opinion about their Smartphone buying and usage behavior. The respondents of this study were arts and science students studying in Government and private colleges in cuddalore district. The researcher personally met the respondents, and data collection has been done only after establishing personal rapport with the respondents. The researcher has totally collected 100 responses for the present study. Hence, the sample of 100 is considered for this study and a total of 100 responses were obtained between the period of August 2019 and October 2019.

Collection of Secondary Data

The researcher collected secondary data on Smartphone sales trends, consumer satisfaction, various factors influencing in the purchase action. This information has been collected from Journals, Magazines, Reports and company's News Bulletin and Internet sources.

Statistical Tools Used

First hand information is collected from 100 respondents. Responses were coded and data entered and then analysed using a computer programme called Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) 20.0 to get inferences. Descriptive analysis were used to describe the sample, to show the numbers and percentage of items into categories, percentage analysis, Pearson Chi-Square test, and ranking method were used for this study.

Limitations of the Study

The result obtained from this study is valid up to a certain extent only. Though there are different segments in Smartphone users, the researcher has selected only under graduate college students studying in arts and science stream. However, the findings of the present study may not be generalized to other segment of the users. Moreover, the data have been collected from the under graduate college students studying in arts and science stream in Cuddalore districts of Tamilnadu only.

Data Analysis and Interpretations

Table – 1 Profile of the Respondents

Factors		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percent
Gender	Male	37	37.0	37.0
	Female	63	63.0	100.0
Type of Family	Nuclear Family	12	12.0	12.0
	Joint Family	88	88.0	100.0
Marital Status	Married	14	14.0	14.0
	Unmarried	86	86.0	100.0

Source: Primary Data

Totally 100 respondents were considered for this study. Among the respondents 37% of the respondents were male and 63% of respondents were female. Regarding the type of family 12% of the respondents belongs to nuclear family and rest of the 88% of the respondents belongs to joint family. And from the data it is identified that 14% of the respondents were married respondents and 86% of them were unmarried. From the data it is found that most of the respondents were female and most of the respondents come from joint family and unmarried.

Table -2 Brand of Smartphone used by the Respondents

BRAND				
		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Apple	3	3.0	3.0
	Samsung	25	25.0	28.0
	Sony	5	5.0	33.0
	Honor	6	6.0	39.0
	Oppo	2	2.0	41.0
	Vivo	13	13.0	54.0
	Mi/Redmi	46	46.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

Among the respondents 46% of them used Mi/Redmi brand of Smartphone, 25% of the respondents have used Samsung Smartphone and rest of the respondents used other brands of Smartphone such as Vivo (13%), Honor (6%), Sony (5%), Apple (3%), Oppo (2%). From the analysis it is observed that most of the respondents used Mi/Redmi brand followed by Samsung.

Table – 3 Factors influenced to buy Smartphone

GENDER Factors Influenced Cross tabulation								
			Factors					Total
			Price	Offers	Features	Advertisement	Performance	
GENDER	Male	Count	15	6	21	6	12	37
		% within GENDER	40.5%	16.2%	56.8%	16.2%	32.4%	
	Female	Count	23	12	16	1	14	63
		% within GENDER	36.5%	19.0%	25.4%	1.6%	22.2%	
Total		Count	38	18	37	7	26	100
Percentages and totals are based on respondents.								
a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.								

Source: Primary Data

Table shows that the factors influenced the respondents to buy a Smartphone. Among the respondents 56.8% of the male respondents and 25.4% of the female respondents gives more importance to features of the Smartphone, 40.5% of the male respondents and 36.5% of the female respondents considered price of the Smartphone during the purchase. Performance of the Smartphone is considered by 32.4% of the male and 22.2% of the female. Respondents given less importance to advertisement of the Smartphone (16.2% male & 1.6% female) and offers offered by the seller (16.2% male & 19.0% female). It is observed from the study that the respondents gave more importance to Price, features and performance of the Smartphone than offers and advertisement.

Table -4 Mode of Purchase of Smartphone

MODE OF PURCHASE				
		Frequency	Percentage	Cumulative Percentage
Valid	Online	32	32.0	32.0
	Show room	68	68.0	100.0
	Total	100	100.0	

Source: Primary Data

From the table it is noted that among the respondents 68% of the respondents purchase their favorites Smartphone from Brand show rooms and 32% of the respondents purchase Smartphone through online purchase. It is observed from the analysis that most of the respondents purchase their favorite Smartphone from show rooms.

Table -5 Most preferred Brand of Smartphone with Reason

BRAND – Preference to buy a Smartphone – Cross tabulation									
			Reason to buy a Brand					Total	
			Features	Performance	Status	Friends	Others		
BRAND	Apple	Count	1	1	1	0	0	2	
		% within BRAND	50.0%	50.0%	50.0%	0.0%	0.0%		
	Samsung	Count	11	1	5	12	1	25	
		% within BRAND	44.0%	4.0%	20.0%	48.0%	4.0%		
	Sony	Count	4	3	1	0	0	5	
		% within BRAND	80.0%	60.0%	20.0%	0.0%	0.0%		
	Honor	Count	5	2	0	1	0	6	
		% within BRAND	83.3%	33.3%	0.0%	16.7%	0.0%		
	Oppo	Count	1	2	0	0	0	2	
		% within BRAND	50.0%	100.0%	0.0%	0.0%	0.0%		
	Vivo	Count	7	4	5	3	2	13	
		% within BRAND	53.8%	30.8%	38.5%	23.1%	15.4%		
	Mi/Redmi	Count	11	6	8	16	4	47	
		% within BRAND	88.0%	72.2%	44.0%	66.0%	78.1%		
	Total		Count	29	13	12	16	3	100
	Percentages and totals are based on respondents.								
	a. Dichotomy group tabulated at value 1.								

Source: Primary Data

In this study Smartphone brands such as Apple, Samsung, Sony, Honor, Oppo, Vivo, Mi/Redmi was considered as a most preferred brands by the respondents. Among the brands 47% of the respondents used Mi/Redmi Smartphone, the reason behind their purchase was features of Smartphone ((88%), performance (72.2%), suggested by friends (66%), status to hold the particular brand of Smartphone (44%), and other reason (78.1%). Samsung Smartphone was preferred by 25% of the respondents and the reason behind their purchase was the suggestion from their friends (48.0%), features of the brand (44%), and status to hold the brand (20%), and followed by performance (4%) and other reasons (4%). Among the respondents 13% of them prefer to buy Vivo Smartphone, the reason was features (53.8%), status (38.5%), performance (30.8%), suggestion from friends (23.1%), and other reasons (15.4%). From the analysis it is found that most preferred brand by the respondents was Mi/Redmi, followed by Samsung and Vivo, and least preferred brand was Honor (6%), Sony (5%), Apple (2%) and Oppo (2%).

Table – 6 Usage of Smartphone

Purpose of Smart Phone	Ranking										
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Phone Call	70	9	5	7	2	3	1	1	2	7	9
Browsing	4	3	7	11	4	8	11	9	9	22	21
e-mail		5	12	5	6	3	18	8	14	19	10
Shopping	2			1	9	7	10	16	24	16	15
Travel Planning	1	1		8		9	15	16	15	21	22
Social Media	6	21	13	5	19	7	8	11	11	5	4
News	2	4	5	7	13	15	12	18	8	11	5
Listen Music	1	7	24	18	17	12	2	7	9	1	2
Taking Picture	2	15	16	22	11	7	5	4	3	5	10
Watching Movie	6	8	7	8	16	24	9	6	4	4	8
Messaging	8	30	11	8	13	6	9	3	3	5	4

Source: Primary Data

In this analysis the respondents were asked to rank their preference and express their behavior towards usage of Smartphone, among the respondents 70% of them used their Smartphone for making calls and ranked first, 30% of the respondents used their Smartphone for messaging and ranked second, 24% of the respondents used their Smartphone to listen music and ranked third, 22% of the respondents used their Smartphone for taking selfie/pictures and ranked fourth, 19% of the respondents used their Smartphone for social media and ranked fifth, 24% of the respondents used their Smartphone for watching movies and ranked sixth, 18% of the respondents used their Smartphone for e-mail and watching news and ranked seventh and eighth rank respectively, 24% of the respondents used their Smartphone for shopping and ranked ninth, 22% of the respondents used their Smartphone for browsing and ranked tenth and 22% of the respondents used their Smartphone for travel planning. From the analysis It is found that most of

the respondents used their Smartphone for making call and given first priority (70%), followed by messaging (30%) and ranked second and they ranked last for travel planning (22%).

Table – 7 Place of use of Smartphone

GENDER - Use of Smartphone Cross tabulation							
			Place of Use Smart Phone				Total
			At Travel	At Home	Free Time	Feel Bored	
GENDER	Male	Count	5	8	23	16	37
		% within GENDER	13.5%	21.6%	62.2%	43.2%	
		% of Total	5.0%	8.0%	23.0%	16.0%	37.0%
	Female	Count	14	19	24	40	63
		% within GENDER	22.2%	30.2%	38.1%	63.5%	
		% of Total	14.0%	19.0%	24.0%	40.0%	63.0%
Total		Count	19	27	47	56	100
		% of Total	19.0%	27.0%	47.0%	56.0%	100.0%
Percentages and totals are based on respondents.							
a. Group							

Source: Primary Data

Table shows the respondents usage behavior of the Smartphone, among the respondents 56% of the respondents used their Smartphone when they feel bored (16% male & 40% female), 47% of the respondents used their Smartphone when they found free time (23% male & 24% female), 27% of respondents used their Smartphone when they are at home (8% male & 19% female) and 19% respondents used their Smartphone during travel time (5% male & 14% female). From the analysis it is found that most of the respondents used their Smartphone when they feel bored and found free time.

Findings

- ✓ From the study the researcher found that most of the respondents were female and most of the respondents come from joint family and unmarried.
- ✓ Among the respondents 46% of them used Mi/Redmi Smartphone, 25% of the respondents have used Samsung Smartphone and other respondents used other brands of Smartphone such as Vivo (13%), Honor (6%), Sony (5%), Apple (3%), Oppo (2%).
- ✓ It is observed from the study that the respondents given more importance to Price, features and performance of the Smartphone than offers and advertisement when they buy Smartphone.
- ✓ It is found that most of the respondents preferred to buy their favorite Smartphone from show rooms than online purchase.

- ✓ It is found that most preferred brand by the respondents was Mi/Redmi, followed by Samsung, Vivo and least preferred brand was Honor (6%), Sony (5%), Apple (2%) and Oppo (2%).
- ✓ among the respondents 70% of them used their Smartphone for making calls and given first in ranking, 30% of the respondents used their Smartphone for messaging and given second in ranking, 50% of the respondents used their Smartphone for social media and ranked third and they given least importance to travel planning.

Conclusion

As the technology is growing the social media has become the routine for each and every students, some students are seen addicted with these technology every day. False information can lead the education system to failure, social media can abuse the society by invading on people's privacy, some useless blogs can influence youth that can become violent and can take some inappropriate actions. Use of social media is beneficial but should be used in a limited way without getting addicted. In the study conducted, majority of the student's opinion was that these sites are used for making friends and studies, so if the students use their Smartphone with social responsibility, they can make good use of Social media and develop their skill and knowledge.

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